

1D SQUEEZE FLOW ANALYSIS OF CHOPPED LONG FIBRE THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Long fibre thermoplastic (LFTs) in the form of chopped tapes are well known as they combine relatively high mechanical performance and good formability compared to respectively short and continuous fibre reinforced composites. Complex shapes can be manufactured with high fibre content with compression moulding [1], which makes these thermoplastic composite chopped tapes a good candidate for industrial applications. During moulding, the flow of fibre reinforced polymer leads to an altered fibre orientation distribution which affects the final mechanical properties of the part [1-4]. In order to predict the mechanical performance, it is therefore important to understand the mould filling behaviour of the LFTs. In spite of being used in the industry for quite a long time, the complex flow behaviour of LFTs in processes like compression moulding is still a challenge to predict. Although the flow in the compression moulding process is usually limited, it is critical for the final part quality. In flat geometries, it is not known whether flow during mould filling is affine/single-phase where polymer and fibres move together or dual-phase where they move separately, which can result in fibre-matrix separation. In order to model the compression moulding process, one needs to know either single- or dual-phase flow is applicable. The objective of this work is to investigate the separation of the resin from fibres and to realize this objective, 1D squeeze flow experiments are performed in a flat geometry. Chopped unidirectional tapes of carbon/polyethersulfone were used for the experiments. Different processing conditions were used in experiments with a mould which was filled only partially. A burn-off method was used to analyze the fibre mass fraction. The samples for the burn-off test were taken along the flow direction. Results of polymer burn-off did not show significant changes in the fibre mass fraction along the flow direction and therefore the flow can be assumed to behave as a single-phase flow.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of thermoplastic composites (TPCs) in the aerospace and automotive industry is increasing steadily. TPCs are well known for their rapid processing, performance, high production rates and recyclability [1,5-6]. The TPC parts found in the aerospace industry typically feature continuous fibre reinforcements, as they offer good mechanical performance and therefore allow parts to be structurally loaded. However, the continuous fibre architecture puts a limit on the achievable part complexity. On the contrary, short fibre thermoplastics (SFTs) can be used to manufacture parts with intricate features which however lack aerospace-level mechanical properties. Long fibre thermoplastic (LFTs) is an excellent candidate to bridge this gap of mechanical performance and shape complexity between continuous and short fibre reinforcements. Figure 1 illustrates the balance between shape complexity and mechanical properties. It can be clearly seen that processability and performance are inversely related. The processing of LFTs induces the flow of the fibre reinforced polymer. During this flow, fibre tend to reorient themselves depending on the velocity gradient. Thus, the final achievable part quality depends on the ability of the reinforcing fibres to move along with the polymer.

Chopped tapes are typically processed by compression moulding. During compression moulding there is a flow of fibre reinforced polymer which fills the cavity. In recent work [1,4] it was shown that

during the flow of LFTs in the intricate geometries fiber and matrix tend to move separately, leading to fiber matrix separation. This fibre matrix separation also is known as dual-phase flow, will affect the fibre mass distribution in the part and ultimately the final mechanical properties.

Figure 1: Correlation of achievable part complexity and resulting mechanical properties with respect to fibre length. The depicted trends for shape complexity and mechanical properties are merely a visual representation. Listed manufacturing methods serve as an example of the possibilities.

This article focuses on the investigation of the flow of LFTs during compression moulding in a planar geometry. The main objective is to find whether the flow acts as a single phase, where fibre and matrix flow together at a single velocity, or dual-phase, where they move separately at different velocities. In the following sections, details on the material used and the experimental investigations carried out are presented. Subsequently, the results of the experimental investigations are discussed.

2 MATERIALS

For the experimental work chopped unidirectional (UD) flakes of carbon/polyethersulfone (C/PES) were used, as shown in figure 2. The average dimensions of the UD flakes are $11 \times 3.7 \times 1.1\text{mm}^3$ (length \times width \times thickness). The fibres are oriented along the longitudinal direction of the flakes. The composite density ρ_c of a flake is 1475 kg/m^3 . The flakes have a fiber mass fraction of 30%. Carbon fiber has a density of 1790 kg/m^3 . The density ρ_m of the matrix polymer PES, is 1370 kg/m^3 and its glass transition temperature T_g is $220 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. PES, being amorphous polymer has no melting point and gradually softens above T_g . Therefore PES requires a high processing temperature of $360 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Due to the high water absorption of C/PES flakes, pre-drying of the flakes is required before processing. Therefore flakes have been dried for 6 hours at $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ as advised by the manufacturer.

Figure 2: Photograph of C/PES flakes with average dimensions of $11 \times 3.7 \times 1.1\text{mm}^3$ (length \times width \times thickness).

3 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

LFTs are usually processed by compression moulding. It allows product manufacturing with complex geometries like thickness transition, sharp corners, ribs, bosses etc. This process also allows for retaining a high fibre volume fraction. Production in large series and improved part performance are some of the advantages that compression moulding has over injection moulding.

Figure 3 shows a typical compression moulding process of C/PES flakes, where the process conditions for a complete compression moulding cycle are illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Typical compression moulding process.

The compression moulding process starts with the placement of a charge of LFT in the form of chopped flakes in the mould (stage i). When the desired processing temperature is reached (stage ii), the mould is closed rapidly by applying a squeezing force (stage iii). Flow is initiated by the squeeze force, which fills the mould cavity with fibre reinforced polymer. Depending on the compound placement and tool design, the material initially flows in the plane on the macro-scale with increasing squeeze force. Upon reaching an out-of-plane mould boundary, the melt front might experience uniaxial flow along with the mould-melt interface. Finally, the moulding compound consolidates as it undergoes (triaxial) compression for a certain consolidation dwell time (τ_{dwell}) [1]. During consolidation, entrapped voids are squeezed out of the charge and/or dissolve in the polymer, as a result densifying the fiber suspension. Once the part is consolidated, the part is cooled (stage iv) and demolded (stage v) at the desired temperature. A net-shape part is obtained in one shot, i.e. it requires almost no post-processing, such as trimming.

Figure 4: Typical process cycle in compression moulding with different stages i) Filling; ii) Heating; iii) Consolidation dwell; iv) Cooling; v) Demolding [1].

In the current work, as the main focus is to study the flow of LFTs in planar geometries, the compression moulding process is slightly modified. First, instead of filling the mould entirely, only two opposite sides of the mould are filled with the charge, as shown in figure 5(a). The dimensions of the mould are $250 \times 250 \text{ mm}^2$. With this setting, a greater flow length of fiber reinforced polymer can be obtained. Secondly, different dwell times were applied and the pressure was removed during cool down. By doing so, the flow length could be found as a function of dwell time (at constant press force and temperature), as seen in Figure 5(b). Six different dwell times were studied, between 6 and 600 seconds, based on previous work at the TPRC [7]. It was observed that the flow distance increases with time, while the thickness of the sample decreased.

Figure 5: Top) Schematic of the experimental setup used for the 1D squeeze flow experiment. Bottom) (Left to right) Samples with increasing dwell time.

Sample Number	Dwell time (s)	Heating force (kN)	Dwell force (kN)	Temperature ($^{\circ}C$)
1	6	6	37.5	360
2	19	6	37.5	360
3	38	6	37.5	360
4	60	6	37.5	360
5	240	6	37.5	360
6	600	6	37.5	360

Table 1: Experimental settings.

4 ANALYSIS

The main objective of this work is to study the flow of LFTs and to identify whether the flow is single phase or dual phase. Flow behaviour is related to strain rate and as a rule of thumb, low strain rate situations are prone to induce strong migration phenomena [8]. Low strain rates (low \dot{h}) are mostly accompanied by low exerted forces when the flow is not stuck. If these forces are close to the yield stress τ_y acting at the fiber contact interface, the fibers experience a relatively high resistance to flow and polymer matrix migrates through the permeable fibrous network.

The fibre mass fraction m_f is locally affected due to percolation as the fiber network densifies when the matrix is separated from it. Therefore, by identifying the fiber mass fraction along the flow direction, insight can be provided into the degree of percolation during flow.

A specimen with the largest flow length is chosen for the analysis of the fibre mass fraction evolution. From figure 6, it can be seen that specimen with a dwell time of 600 seconds have a higher squeezed width and thus experienced the most flow. A sample of $39 \times 39 \text{ mm}^2$ on average was cut from the squeezed specimens. Samples were prepared from different locations along the flow length, being start, middle and end. The specimen were dried for 6 hours at 15°C with 10% relative humidity to exclude the moisture effects.

Figure 6: Squeezed width of six specimens plotted against dwell time.

In order to analyze the fibre mass content, a burn-off test (in oven) protocol was developed based on the thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA). The optimum test conditions (time and temperature) were found using TGA. In the oven, the larger specimens were heated for 2 hours at a high temperature of 550°C in air/nitrogen?. By doing so, the polymer matrix is decomposed and dry fibre residual is obtained. By measuring the residual fibre mass, the fibre mass fraction can be calculated, assuming negligible fibre degradation during the process.

TGA was also used for the analysis of the composite material, although in that case, the sample size was small (50mg).

Figure 7: Left) Sample for the oven before and after burning. Right) Sample for TGA before and after burning.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The averaged results for the fibre mass fraction in the oven and TGA are shown in figure 8. It can be seen that there is no significant trend for fibre mass fraction as a function of flow length. Error bars show overlap and therefore there is no evidence that the compound behaves as a two-phase flow in the current range of applied shear rates. Therefore it can be assumed that the flow field is single-phase and the fibre and matrix move together. From figure 8, it can also be seen that the measured fibre mass fraction shows an offset of approximately 5 % compared to the 30 % weight fraction of C/PES flakes were engineered to contain. This mass reduction is considered to be a side effect due to the air atmosphere during the burn-off experiments [9]. Presence of oxygen is a requirement for full vaporization of the PES polymer chains, but it reacts with the carbon fibres as well. As a result, both PES and carbon fibre will decompose during the experimental procedure. It is, nonetheless, assumed that the oxidation of the fibres does not affect the relative trend in Figure 8 and the thereon based hypothesis of affine/single phase flow, because all tests were conducted under equal conditions.

To quantify the fibre mass loss due to oxidation, three piles of pure carbon fibre of approximately 3 g are exposed to the same conditions as specified for burn-off. Afterwards, the mass loss was quantified to be $16.64^{+0.82}_{-0.90}$ %. Now, multiplying with the composite fibre mass fraction of and thereby assuming that the encapsulation of the fibres during burn-off does not affect the oxidation rate, an introduced error during burn-off of $4.99^{+0.26}_{-0.27}$ % is found. When added to the average measured fibre mass fraction of 25% displayed in Figure 8, the mass fraction of the input material is found, which indeed corresponds to the 30% suggested by the manufacturer.

The results of a similar study [10] performed at the TPRC, by taking the same material are shown in figure 9, wherein this case specimens were taken from a circular squeezed disk. Similar burn-off conditions were used in the oven. The same trend was observed there, which confirms the above results.

9 CONCLUSIONS

Long fibre thermoplastics (LFTs), featuring centimetre length fibres, were introduced several decades ago to bridge the gap between the already existing short fibre thermoplastics and continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastics in terms of mechanical properties and shape complexity. Processing of LFTs by compression moulding involves the flow of the material in a mould cavity.

Figure 8: Evolution of the fibre mass fraction in the flow direction. The error bars show the observed minimum and maximum value for the marker point.

Figure 9: Evolution of the fibre mass fraction in a radial flow direction. Markers correspond to the centre points of the taken specimens. The error bars show the observed minimum and maximum value for the marker point.

To obtain greater insight into the processing of LFTs, it is essential to study the flow of the fibre filled resin under representative processing conditions.

The objectives of this work are to understand the evolution of fibre content due to flow and to find out whether the flow is single or dual phase. Squeeze flow experiments were performed with different dwell times. A burn-off method was used and compared with TGA analysis. The fibre mass fraction after

burn-off experiments was measured. The results of the experiments revealed that the squeeze flow of planar geometries was single-phase, and there is no percolation for the studied material within the chosen process window. Fibre and matrix flow together. The results of this study will be applied when modelling the squeeze flow behaviour in planar geometries.

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